

**TU Delft OPEN
Publishing**

- Free to read?
- Free to publish?
- CC BY-4.0
- Authors retain copyright?
- Not for profit?
- Non-university authors?

Science, Technology, and Design

publishing-lib@tudelft.nl

Latest releases

OPEN
PRESS
TiU

- Free to read? ✓
- Free to publish? ✓
- CC BY-4.0 ✓
- Authors retain copyright? ✓
- Not for profit? ✓
- Non-university authors? ✗

Multidisciplinary,
with focus on Social Sciences and
Humanities

openpress@tilburguniversity.edu

Latest releases

University of Groningen Press

- Free to read? ✓
- Free to publish? ✓
- CC BY-NC-SA ✓
- Authors retain copyright? ✓
- Not for profit? ✓
- Non-university authors? ✗

Multidisciplinary

ugp@rug.nl

Latest releases

Maastricht
University
Press

- Free to read?
- Free to publish?
- CC BY-4.0
- Authors retain copyright?
- Not for profit?
- Non-university authors?

Multidisciplinary

mup@maastrichtuniversity.nl

Latest releases

Constanța Roșca

**RADBOD
UNIVERSITY
PRESS**

- Free to read? ✓
- Free to publish? ✓
- CC BY-NC-ND ✓
- Authors retain copyright? ✓
- Not for profit? ✓
- Non-university authors? ✗

Multidisciplinary

radbouduniversitypress@ru.nl

Latest releases

